

Balance of payments adjustment through public absorption an estimation of an ARDL model in a panel of MENA and eastern European countries

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Abstract

One of the most difficult problems in the field of public economic policies and their effects on the fundamental macroeconomic variables lies in their impact on the external sector variables; hence the need to control public expenditure in proportions that are deemed useful and that would be compatible with the objectives set in order to ensure the fundamental balances at both the internal and external levels.

The purpose of this article, from this perspective, is to focus on the balance of payments adjustment through public absorption, for a sample of 11 countries from the MENA region and the European continent. By bursting public absorption in two fundamental components: public consumption and public investment, we highlight how action on these two main components could adjust the balance of payments balances for the selected countries.

Adopting the lessons of the absorption approach, often referred to as fiscal or financial, as a comprehensive approach to balance of payments adjustment, we will estimate an ARDL panel model using advanced panel data modelling techniques. Our empirical results underline the existence of a short- and long-term adjustment relationship between public absorption and external balances, regardless of the method adopted to measure them: external balance of goods and services or current account balance. These empirical results corroborate the prediction of the Keynesian Absorption Hypothesis and reject the Ricardian Hypothesis that there is no link between internal and external balances. Therefore, we discuss the implications of our results to highlight the main measures that would be consistent with macroeconomic adjustment policies, especially for MENA countries where internal and external imbalances are more persistent compared to the European continent.

Keywords: absorption approach, adjustment, balance of payments, public investment, public consumption.

Introduction

During the thirty glorious years as of the end of the Second World War to the end of the 1970s, the developed and developing capitalist countries experienced uninterrupted economic growth. The period in question was characterised by the application of the principles Keynesian theory advocated in the 1930s and marked by accelerated government intervention in the economic and social sphere. In particular, expansionary fiscal policies and high budget deficits were in many cases tolerated both in government and in academic research.

This was no longer the case in the early 1980s when macro-economic and financial imbalances were triggered in most developing countries, with an emphasis on restoring fundamental balances, including those of the state budget and balance of payments, as the ultimate objectives of all governments and economic policy makers.

In the current context, where international trade is an obvious necessity for all countries, the balance of payments is one of the most used documents, particularly by public decision-makers, by international financial organisations and institutions, and by public opinion, to diagnose the evolution of the macroeconomic situation of an economy, particularly in relation to the rest of the world. It is through this statistical and accounting document that the symptoms of an economy could be manifested.

In this framework, the preoccupation of each government or any public decision-maker are to adjust or rebalance the position of the external accounts in order to be more credible to their creditors. But, as L'Heriteau (1986: 142) has pointed out, "*the external deficit is the sign of a problem and not a problem itself, and to use a medical metaphor: the external deficit is the symptom of a disease and not a disease in itself. It is not against it that we must act but against its causes*".

Indeed, explaining the causes of imbalances or rebalancing the balance of payments has long been a major concern of economic theory and international financial institutions, in this case the International Monetary Fund and the World Bank. These theories of types of macroeconomic strategies include actions such as monetary restraint, fiscal adjustment, balance of payments adjustment, reduction of the two main components of public absorption (consumer goods and investment spending) etc. Consequently, it is no coincidence that the IMF attributes the main responsibility for the imbalances to "*an expansionary public spending policy and the increase in the budget deficit. And among the criteria for the implementation of recovery programmes, the omnipresence of the ceiling on credits to the State concretises the junction of*

the monetary approach and the budgetary approach in the IMF's analyses" (see Hériteau, 1986: 128).

This article is in line with this perspective, and deals with the subject of adjustment through public absorption on the balance of payments for a panel of five countries of MENA, including Morocco and five European countries.

The main objective of this research is to shed light on the origins of the economic constraints on the external imbalances of the national economy and, on the other hand, to highlight the main implications of economic policy in order to readjust and ensure a short- and long-term balance of payments balance.

In other words, taking into account the main lessons of the balance of payments absorption approach, this paper will propose an analysis of the fiscal and other determinants of the balance of payments through attempting to answer two main questions. If public deficits lead to external deficits in the balance of payments, then, which component of public absorption is responsible? What would be the magnitude of the respective impact of public consumption and investment? To answer on our question, we will proceed in three distinct but complementary parts. The first part consists of an overview of the theoretical underpinnings and the main empirical works to better understand the complexity of our research subject. In the second part, it is necessary to present the main macroeconomic indicators of the selected countries for the purpose of comparison and analysis. The third and last part, will be devoted to the estimation of a panel model for the selected sample based on advanced techniques in panel econometrics, i.e., ARDL type models, without forgetting to conclude with the main results of our estimation and economic implications.

1. Adjustment through absorption: theoretical underpinnings, literature review of the main empirical works and formulation of the theoretical model

1.1. Place of the absorption approach in the theory of balance of payments adjustment

The theory of balance of payments adjustment is not the work of the present liberal world. Smith, A. (1776), Ricardo, D. (1821) and Mill, J. S. (1849) works testify to the efforts of the classical school in building this theory. That being said, for a very long time one of the major problems of international economic theory was the search for equilibrium through the adjustment or rather the rebalancing of the balance of payments.

Apart from the mercantilist doctrine, which was the dominant analysis in international trade's theory before 1752, and which seeks only a surplus balance, the theory of balance of payments adjustment has been marked by the predominance of three major schools, corresponding to three different conceptions of balance of payments imbalance. The first one is the monetary approach, which addresses the problem as a consequence of a domestic monetary imbalance, i.e. the imbalance of the supply of excess money relative to demand. While the elasticity approach treats the problem as one of successful devaluation to improve the external balance. On the other hand, in the absorption approach, the imbalance in the balance of payments is due to an imbalance between demand and production, whose roots could be mainly explained by the fiscal imbalance.

The monetary approach

The monetary approach to the balance of payments considers the balance of payments as a purely monetary phenomenon. This approach is attributed to David Hume, for whom an imbalance in the balance of trade cannot be sustained. Indeed, an external surplus (deficit) leads to an inflow of gold (outflow), which inflates (shrinks) the money supply; and the resulting inflation (deflation) degrades (improves) competitiveness until equilibrium is established.

This approach originates from the work of IMF economists in the 1960s, namely Mundell and Johnson (Chicago school), Polak, J. J. (1957). In the seventies and eighties, the contributions of Frenkel, J. & Johnson, H. (1976), M. Mussa (1974), Dornbusch (1979) and Branson & al (1979).

The basic monetary model assumes full employment, perfect competition, perfect capital mobility and flexible prices and wages. Despite the extension of the basic monetary model by Dornbusch (1976), the monetary approach is still very restrictive. Indeed, it marginalises the real determinants (the role of trade in goods and services for example). Moreover, certain basic foundations are empirically invalid, notably the perfect substitutability of capital. These

limitations are at the origin of the development of the elasticity approach and the so-called fiscal or financial absorption approach.

The elasticity approach

The elasticity approach was largely developed by Jean Robinson (1937), in a classic article entitled "the foreign exchange", in response to the need to adjust the balance of payments under the flexible exchange rate regime.

This approach considers that the supply of goods and services on international markets is not perfectly elastic and that trade-offs are imperfect. In the event of a trade balance surplus (deficit), the exchange rate appreciates (depreciates) until equilibrium is restored. The variation and volatility of the exchange rate are all the more important as the price elasticities of foreign trade are low. Furthermore, Krugman and Obstfeld (1994) explain the erratic exchange rate variations after 1973 by the slowdown in the reaction of trade flows to exchange rate variations due to the irreversibility of the investments necessary for exports.

However, the conventional relationship between the exchange rate and the trade balance is not always verified. In this regard, the absorption approach comes to fill the gaps of the elasticity approach through focusing on the role of income elasticities of foreign trade.

The absorption approach

The inefficiency of the balance of payments adjustment under the elasticity approach is due to the partial equilibrium analysis; it ignores supply-side conditions and cost changes as a result of devaluation (depreciation), and it tends to neglect expenditure and income effects following exchange rate changes. Furthermore, the monetary approach to the balance of payments is not the sole method used by the IMF. It is complemented by an analysis in terms of income and absorption using Keynesian concepts and reasoning. Firstly, with regard to inflation, the origin of which is attributed to an excess of aggregate demand over available supply, this excess being due to too much distributed income. At the same time, the balance of payments deficit is identified as an excess of "absorption" over national income.

The absorption approach was originally developed in the early 1950s at the IMF by Sidney Alexander (1952), and later elaborated by Harry Johnson (1958) in his seminal paper "Towards a General Theory of the Balance of Payments". This work shows that the rebalancing of the external balance in the presence of an imbalance is not only done by adjusting the exchange rate but also by changing the level of income. Indeed, in the case of a decrease in exports, the resulting drop in the level of income reduces the level of imports and consequently limits the degree of depreciation necessary to level the trade balance deficit.

1.2 Formulation of the basic model of the absorption approach

Using concepts and reasoning inspired by Keynes (1936), the absorption approach relies on the assumption of price flexibility and automatic demand adjustment, as noted by Nyahoho, E. (2002), an assumption that the facts seem to disprove. Moreover, the explanation of a deterioration in the balance of payments by consumption expenditure exceeding domestic production does not recognise external shocks as sources of imbalance.

The absorption approach attributes the origin of inflation to an excess of aggregate demand over available supply. This excess is explained by a large amount of distributed income. The balance of payments deficit is finally justified by an excess of absorption over national income.

In order to present this basic relationship between absorption and the balance of trade in the basic model of the budgetary approach, we rely on the basic identity of national accounting:

$$Y = C + I + X - M \quad (1.1)$$

Assuming that:

$$A = C + I \quad (1.2)$$

$$B = X - M \quad (1.3)$$

A = being the absorption of goods and services which is equal to the share of national income devoted to domestic expenditure.

B = the balance of trade

From equations (1.2) and (1.3), we can write:

$$Y = A + B \quad (1.4)$$

$$B = Y - A \quad (1.5)$$

Furthermore, equation (1.1) shows the relationship between absorption and the balance of trade, as a deficit or surplus in the balance of trade has its counterpart: "a country living beyond its means" or "a country living below its means".

According to the analysis of the trade multiplier (Bourguinat, H. 2007), the trade balance can improve if and only if income (Y) increases or absorption (A) decreases. In the case where the economy operates in a context of full employment (where the economy has very strong supply rigidities), then it becomes necessary to reduce absorption (A) to improve the trade balance (B).

The problem of reducing absorption (A) in order to reduce the balance of payments balance is the fundamental point of our research, through the problem of fiscal adjustment of the balance of payments; this raises the very important question of the impact of the adjustment of public absorption on the external balance (B).

Indeed, the most important component of absorption (A) is made up of public absorption, notably public consumption (C_{pub}) and public investment (I_{pub}) which are grouped together in public expenditure (G).

To show the importance of the adjustment of the budget balance on the external balance, equation (1.1) of the national accounts can be written as follows:

With: C_p: Private consumption, C_{pub}: Public consumption, I_p: Private investment, I_{pub}: Public investment, X: Exports, M: Imports, T: Government revenue, G: Government expenditure and S_p: Private savings.

$$Y = C_p + C_{pub} + I_p + I_{pub} + X - M \quad (1.6)$$

$$C = C_p + C_{pub} \quad (1.7)$$

$$I = I_p + I_{pub} \quad (1.8)$$

$$G = C_{pub} + I_{pub} \quad (1.9)$$

Replacing (1.9) in (1.6), we have:

$$Y = C_p + I_p + G + X - M \quad (1.10)$$

The national income can also be written as follows:

$$Y = C_p + T + S_p \quad (1.11)$$

Using equations (1.10) and (1.11), we can write:

$$C_p + T + S_p = C_p + I_p + G + X - M \quad (1.12)$$

That is:

$$(S_p - I_p) + (T - G) - (X - M) = 0 \quad (1.13)$$

Equation (1.13) means that the sum of the private and public financial balances is equal to the current account balance. Due to the postulate of private sector rationality, its financial balance (S_p-I_p) is generally stable and balanced in the long run while the public financial balance(T-G)

is generally negative and persistent, as pointed out by Mansouri, B. (2003) The external balance (X-M) can thus only be negative because, quite simply, the public sector spends more than it can produce.

This means the place and importance of public absorption adjustment in any action to correct balance of payments imbalances, which gives the fiscal approach to the balance of payments a primary importance as a general theory of the balance of payments that has convergences with other macroeconomic adjustment approaches.

1.3 Literature review of empirical work

Despite the existence of a relatively large theoretical literature dealing with the issue, the arguments and work that has been done on the subject are still controversial. In developed countries, the issue is not empirically resolved. In developing countries, the results of empirical work are still mixed.

In other words, the empirical studies on balance of payments adjustment through public absorption carried out in both developed and developing countries present results that can be grouped into three categories: (1) a positive relationship between public absorption expenditure and balance of payments adjustment, (2) no relationship between public expenditure adjustment and balance of payments balances, and (3) confirmation of adjustment through absorption under certain conditions.

The first category of authors shows a positive relationship between fiscal adjustment through public absorption and balance of payments adjustments, which in most cases reduces the goods and services trade balance or the current account balance, and confirms the Keynesian absorption hypothesis which predicts that the accumulation of public deficits is always associated with high external deficits.

In the same vein, we can cite the works that have estimated the VAR model or the VECM model for the United States that have approved the positive effect of public absorption on the current account balance: Enders & Lee (1990); Rosensweig & Tallman (1993); Bahmani-Oskooee (1995) etc.

Similarly, Roubini (1991) estimates argue in favour of a causal relationship from budget deficits to current account deficits, thus supporting the twin deficits hypothesis. Also, Anderson (1990) concluded that a reduction in the budget deficit leads to a decrease in the external deficit. In the same vein, Darrat (1988), Abell, J.D (1990), Zietz and Pemberton (1990), Bachman (1992), Rosensweig and Tallman (1993), Bahmani-Oskooee (1992, 1995), Vamvoukas (1999) support

the conventional view that the two deficits are closely related and that the external deficits are caused by the components of fiscal deficits.

As for the empirical work carried out from the 2000s onwards, it has benefited from the development of econometric modelling techniques. Thus, Chinn & Prasad (2003) confirmed the relationship of a positive adjustment between public expenditure adjustments and the current account balance, which was estimated using a panel model for 18 industrialised countries and 71 developing countries. Beetsma (2008) confirmed that the increase in public spending worsens the external balance for 14 countries by estimating a VAR model for 14 European countries. Using the classical panel fixed effects and dynamic panel data model for 33 European countries, Forte & Magazzino (2013) showed that fiscal spending that led to chronic budget deficits also generates external deficits.

Recently, the impact of public absorption on balance of payments balances has been analysed by Bousnina, & al. (2021) who confirmed that the existence of chronic fiscal and other external imbalances and macroeconomic risks are related to public absorption. Afonso, A. & al (2022) used an estimation method based on panel data techniques, they confirmed the twin deficits hypothesis in 65 countries with fiscal rules. They found that this hypothesis is confirmed when expenditure budget rules are taken into account other than revenue rules.

The second category of authors validates the relationship between the budget deficit, notably through public expenditure, and the balance of payments deficit under certain conditions. As an example, we can cite the work of Nickel and Vansteenkiste (2008) who confirmed the relationship between the two deficits for 22 industrialised countries, through the estimation of a threshold effect model of panel data, and argued that the said relationship is verified when the threshold of the public debt of GDP is within the limit of 90%, beyond this threshold the hypothesis of the Ricardian equivalence is confirmed. Daly and Siddiki (2009) confirmed the relationship between the two deficits through the estimation of a VECM model for a panel of 23 OECD countries. However, this number decreases if structural breaks are not taken into account. In the same vein, Nickel and Tudyka (2014) estimated a dynamic VAR model for a panel of 17 European countries with a public debt ratio above 70%, and confirmed that an increase in public spending leads to an increase in the trade balance, whereas such a relationship takes the opposite direction above a certain level of public debt.

The third category of authors considers a weak or non-existent relationship between the two deficits, they do not give any importance to the variation of the main compositions of public absorption on the deterioration of external imbalances. Among the empirical studies that

support the Ricardian equivalence hypothesis that budget and external deficits are not related, we can mention the works of Miller and Russek (1989), Dewald and Ulan (1989), Kim (1995), Normandin (1999).

Within this framework, Normandin (1999) evaluated the causal relationship between the external deficit and the budget deficit for Canada and the U.S. using the overlapping generations model proposed by Blanchard (1985). This model nests the twin deficits hypothesis and the Ricardian equivalence hypothesis. The model implies that consumers predict future government deficits based on the evolution of the two deficits. Such an implication has led to restrictions to be tested for certain consumer planning horizons. For the Canadian case, "the relevant (possibly long) horizons and the persistence of the budget deficit imply responses that are statistically positive", an empirical result consistent with the dynamic deficit hypothesis of the budget deficit is not statistically positive, suggesting that "the persistence of the budget deficit is not a major determinant of the relationship between the two deficits, so that Ricardian equivalence appears to be a useful proxy for the US economy".

With regard to empirical work from the 2000s onwards, studies by Kaufmann (2002) on Austria and Kouassi & al. (2004) for 10 developed countries that estimated a VECM model and causality in the Granger sense are cited. Muller & Corsetti (2008) estimated the structural VAR model and also showed the limited impact of government spending and the resulting fiscal shocks on the external balance in the US and Australia, where the fiscal balance has no significant impact on the current account. Furthermore, Kim and Roubini (2008) through the estimation of a VAR model, they also confirmed the twin divergence between the internal and external deficits; hence the absence of a direct effect of absorption on the balance adjustment. Recently, Eyraud, & al (2018) and Beetsma, & al (2019) have shown that stricter fiscal rules, especially on public spending, induce a stronger Ricardian equivalence, as private agents expect the government to reduce the budget deficit in the future. This reduces the impact of the fiscal balance on the current account and therefore neutralises any balance of payments adjustment manoeuvre by public absorption.

After presenting the theoretical underpinnings and the formulation of the theoretical model of the balance of payments adjustment, we will introduce in the following the main economic specificities of the countries constituting the selected panel, before estimating and discussing the results obtained.

2. Main macroeconomic aggregates of the sample countries

In order to draw the main implications of balance of payments adjustment policies, notably through action on public expenditure for the Moroccan economy, it proved necessary to select, in addition to Morocco, 5 similar countries from the MENA region and 5 other countries from the European continent.

2.1. MENA countries

The selected MENA countries were selected for two main reasons. First, because they have common specifications in terms of their economic structure, as they are not among the oil-producing countries of the region where the impact of the equilibrium relationship can be exerted inversely, through export revenues to the fiscal balance, as demonstrated by Alkswani (2000). Second, because they are linked to the Moroccan economy through bilateral and/or multilateral trade agreements.

In sum, the panel that belongs to the MENA region includes: Morocco, Tunisia, Egypt, Jordan, Turkey and Lebanon. The table below provides a summary of the evolution of the main macroeconomic indicators, relating to both the internal and external sectors, before the outbreak of the covid-19 crisis.

Table 01: Main recent macroeconomic indicators of the MENA countries in the sample

Countries	Egypt		Jordan		Lebanon		Morocco		Tunisia		Turkey	
	2018	2019	2018	2019	2018	2019	2018	2019	2018	2019	2018	2019
GDP, constant prices (percent change)	5,31	5,56	1,93	1,96	-1,66	-7,28	3,15	2,61	2,72	0,98	2,98	0,89
GDP, current prices (Billions USD)	250,25	302,34	42,99	44,57	55,28	52,37	118,10	119,87	40,14	39,17	779,69	760,52
Inflation (%)	20,85	13,88	4,45	0,68	4,55	2,90	1,57	0,24	7,31	6,72	16,33	15,18
General government net lending/borrowing (% GDP)	-9,44	-7,99	-4,66	-6,01	-11,22	-10,30	-3,70	-3,82	-4,54	-3,86	-3,79	-5,61
General government gross debtt (% GDP)	92,48	84,21	75,06	78,02	154,02	171,11	65,20	65,07	80,08	74,17	30,17	32,66
Current account balance (Billions USD)	-5,96	-10,89	-2,97	-0,95	-15,73	-14,44	-6,22	-4,41	-4,44	-3,29	-21,74	6,76
Current account balance (% GDP)	-2,38	-3,60	-6,90	-2,13	-28,45	-27,57	-5,27	-3,68	-11,07	-8,39	-2,79	0,89

Source : FMI - World Economic Outlook Database October 2021

The main point of similarity between these countries lies in the economic model adopted, which can be described as a hybrid system in that it is based on a market economy, and at the same time the state plays a significant role in economic emergence and macroeconomic regulation. Taking this situation into account, it is understood that the intervention of the governments of these countries through the budgetary instrument, inter alia, public consumption and investment expenditures can influence the balance of payments balances.

From the observation of the main macroeconomic indicators summarized in the table above, it is clear that the MENA countries in the sample have different economic sizes due to their

divergence in GDP. In addition, their growth rates have not experienced very significant changes with the exception of the Lebanese economy which has experienced an economic contraction as a result of the political and economic crisis that the country has been suffering in recent years.

Other macroeconomic indicators differ from country to country. However, it was found that although the public finance balance and the current account balance have different levels, it was in deficit for all countries except for the economy of Turkey which has entered into a small current account surplus for the year 2019.

2.2. European Countries

In order to give the econometric models a larger number of observations per individual, it was deemed appropriate to enlarge the sample panel by selecting another group of countries belonging to a different region other than the MENA countries, but which manifest economic similarities.

In this context, five Eastern European countries were selected, four of which were members of the Eastern bloc, in addition to Greece which was influenced in parallel by communist policies where State intervention is the most important determinant of economic choices and macroeconomic regulation.

As for the four European countries of the former Eastern Bloc, the panel considers Romania, Poland, Hungary and Bulgaria, which experienced an economic system similar to that of the USSR (Union of Soviet Socialist Republics). After the collapse of the Eastern Bloc, the Soviet model gave way to a liberal development model in the European countries known as satellites of the USSR, including the countries in our sample, their main economic indicators are as follows:

Table 02: Main recent macroeconomic indicators for the European countries in the sample

macro-economic indicators \ Countries	Bulgaria		Hungary		Poland		Romania		Greece	
	2018	2019	2018	2019	2018	2019	2018	2019	2018	2019
GDP, constant prices (percent change)	3,09	3,69	5,40	4,64	5,35	4,75	4,48	4,13	1,56	1,86
GDP, current prices (Billions USD)	66,29	68,56	160,43	163,49	587,43	597,19	241,46	249,70	212,35	205,35
Inflation (%)	2,63	2,46	2,85	3,37	1,60	2,31	4,63	3,83	0,77	0,52
General government net lending/borrowing (% GDP)	0,12	-0,96	-2,10	-2,08	-0,24	-0,69	-2,82	-4,56	0,81	0,23
General government gross debt (% GDP)	20,11	18,40	69,12	65,49	48,82	45,60	36,47	36,82	189,89	184,91
Current account balance (Billions USD)	0,63	1,26	0,48	-0,74	-7,53	2,93	-11,22	-12,21	-7,58	-4,58
Current account balance (% GDP)	0,95	1,83	0,30	-0,45	-1,28	0,49	-4,65	-4,89	-3,57	-2,23

Source : FMI - World Economic Outlook Database October 2021

A comparison of the indicators in the above table with those in Table 2 for MENA countries shows that Eastern European countries, with the exception of Romania, have generally recorded controllable public finance balances of less than 3 per cent for 2019. This can be attributed to the fiscal rules and measures introduced within the European Union. The levels of inflation rates have also remained within non worrying ranges.

In the same trend, the current account of the balance of payments was slightly balanced or close to balance with the exception of Romania and to a lesser extent the economy of Greece which had external deficits exceeding 3% of GDP.

Furthermore, the presentation of macroeconomic indicators for all the countries in the sample, both MENA and Eastern European countries, shows the interrelation between the budget deficit and the current account deficit of the balance of payments. However, in order to further investigate this finding, in the context of a larger sample, it is necessary to estimate such a relationship by adopting panel econometric techniques. To do so, we will first present the variables of the models and the appropriate methodology that will be adopted for a dynamic panel of the ARDL type.

3. Definition of the variables of the selected models and appropriate econometric methodology

After presenting the models to be estimated in this paper, the selected variables and their data sources will be defined before the appropriate methodology of the selected models is considered.

3.1 Econometric models

The main objective of this paper is to investigate the fiscal adjustment of the balance of payments by focusing the analysis not on the budget deficits as such but rather on their structures.

Referring to the basic model of the balance of payments absorption approach formulated above, the structure of public expenditure can be understood through the breakdown of public absorption into two basic components: public consumption and public investment. While the budget deficit has effects that could aggravate balance of payments deficits, as confirmed by several authors cited above, including Darrat (1988); Enders & Lee (1990); Anderson (1990); Roubini (1991); Bachman (1992); Rosensweig & Tallman (1993); Bahmani-Oskooee (1995); Vamvoukas (1999); Prasad (2003); Beetsma (2008); Bousnina, & al. (2021) and Afonso, A. & al. (2022) What would be the magnitude of the respective impact of public consumption and investment?

In order to see how the fundamental components of public absorption could adjust the balance of payments balances in the sample under study, we will conduct in what follows an empirical analysis through the estimation of the relationship between the balance of payments balance on the one hand, and the two main components of public absorption on the other.

In our specification of the balance of payments adjustment relationship through public absorption, we adopt two alternative measures of the balance of payments balances as the variable to be explained (dependent), in contrast to several empirical studies which only take into account one balance, generally the trade balance of goods and services. In a first step, the balance of payments will be measured by the external balance of goods and services. In a second step, the balance of payments will be approximated by the current account balance.

Taking into account the independent (explanatory) variable measured by the Price Level Ratio of the PPP conversion factor (GDP) to the market exchange rate as a control variable next to two main components of public absorption as explanatory variables, we will estimate the following two models:

The first model explains the balance of payments balance by the external balance of goods and services, and directly relates the impact of the adjustment by public absorption on the latter. It designates as the balance of payments SBS, the external balance of goods and services, and the two main components of public absorption by C_{pub} and I_{pub} , respectively public consumption and public investment. The price level ratio of the PPP conversion factor (GDP) to the market exchange rate is explained by the PPPC. Thus, the first model for the 11 countries of the sample including Morocco can be written as follows:

$$SBS_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \cdot C_{pub_{it}} + \beta_2 \cdot I_{pub_{it}} + \beta_3 \cdot PPPC_{it} + \varepsilon_{it} \quad (3.1)$$

The second model seeks to explain the balance of payments balance by the current account balance, and directly relates the impact of the adjustment by public absorption on the latter. Taking into account the same independent variables retained in the first model, the second model can be specified as follows:

$$SC_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \cdot C_{pub_{it}} + \beta_2 \cdot I_{pub_{it}} + \beta_3 \cdot PPPC_{it} + \varepsilon_{it} \quad (3.2)$$

3.2 Appropriate Econometric Methodology: Use of an ARDL-Panel

The two models used to estimate the adjustment of the balance of payments by public absorption are based on panel data. The latter are also called longitudinal data which can be seen as an aggregation of individual data taken at several dates Duguet, E. (2014).

Thus, this aggregation offers a greater amount of information that should allow for better estimation of structural relationships encountered in economics and for more efficient results compared to time series data on a single individual.

Unlike some empirical studies that have attempted to estimate the relationship between internal and external balances for a group of countries while using traditional panel data econometrics, this paper uses advanced panel techniques. In this framework, we estimate an error-correction model in panel data that incorporates the lags of the variables contained in the model to capture the long-run dynamics.

Indeed, the principle of estimating ECMs in the panel framework follows the same logic as for time series. The stationarity test and the order of integration of the series must be used to determine the choice of model to be estimated.

The steps for estimating an MCE in panel data are as follows:

1. Test for stationarity of the variables;
2. Co-integration test (optional);
3. Optimal lag with the SIC graph;
4. Estimation of the VAR, VECM and ARDL model;
5. Interpretation of long- and short-term relationships (coefficients);
6. Validation and re-estimation of the model (depending on the optimal model chosen).

Given that the type of model is an ARDL panel, the generalized ARDL (p,q,q,...p) model can be specified as follows:

$$7. Y_{it} = \sum_{j=1}^p \delta_i Y_{i,t-j} + \sum_{j=0}^q \beta'_{ij} X_{i,t-j} + \varphi_i + e_{it}$$

Where: Y_{it} is the dependent variable, $(X'_{i,t})'$ is a $k \times 1$ vector of variables that must be integrated with different orders, δ_{ij} is the coefficient of the lagged dependent variable called *scalars*, β_{ij} are $k \times 1$ coefficient vectors, φ_i is the unit specific fixed effect, $i=1, \dots, N$, $t=1, 2, \dots, T$, p and q are optimal lag orders and e_{it} is the error term.

The re-parameterized ARDL (p,q,q,...q) error correction model can be specified as follows:

$$Y_{it} = \sum_{j=1}^p \delta_i Y_{i,t-j} + \sum_{j=0}^q \beta'_{ij} X_{i,t-j} + \varphi_i + e_{it}$$

Where: $\theta = -(1 - \delta_i)$ is the group-specific speed of adjustment coefficient (must be < 0), λ' is the vector of the long-run relationship. $ECT = [Y_{i,t-1} - \lambda'_{i,t} X_{i,t}]$ is the error correction term. And ξ_{ij} et β'_{ij} are the coefficient of short – run dynamic

To estimate the ARDL panel, there are three estimation methods based on the estimation of a panel ARDL:

- **Pooled Mean Group (PMG):** This estimator allows the intercepts, short-term coefficients and error variances to differ freely between groups, but constrains the long-term coefficients to be the same. The long-term coefficients are the same. It can be seen as an intermediate tool between the MG and the DFE;
- **Mean Group (MG):** this estimator is proposed by Pesaran and Smith, it consists in doing country by country regressions, it stipulates the absence of restriction. According to Pirotte (1999), the mean group estimator provides efficient estimators in the long run for a large number of individuals;
- **Dynamic Fixed Effect (DFE):** according to this estimator the intercept differs between groups of individuals while the slope and variance of the error are identical.

To validate this type of model, its robustness must be tested according to the Hausman joint test. This test allows us to decide on the most efficient estimator according to the following procedure.

Figure: Hausman test procedure for choosing the optimal estimator

Source: Prepared by the author

3.3. Description of variables and data sources

The description of the variables and the related data sources are summarised in Table 3 below. In order to estimate the two models mentioned above (equations 3.1 and 3.2), the macroeconomic data comes mainly from the World Bank database (WDI 2021) and covers 11 countries in the sample over the period 1995-2016, which gives a number of 242 observations for the two models selected.

The table below presents a summary of the variables selected as well as the data sources used for both the dependent and independent variables.

Table 03: Definitions of selected variables and data sources

Variable	Meaning	Main data source	Secondary data sources
SBS	External balance of goods and services % GDP	WDI: 16/12/2021	****
SC	Current account balance (% of GDP)		WEO: Lebanon (1995-2001)
CPUB	General government final consumption expenditure (% of GDP)		****
PPPC	Price level ratio of PPP conversion factor (GDP) to market exchange rate		****
IPUB	Net investment in nonfinancial assets (% of GDP)		Morocco: 1996, 2000, 2001 (Manar Stata) Tunisia: 2013-2016 (Central Bank of Tunisia Report) Turkey: 1999-2007 (Capital Budgeting and Public Investment Management-Turkey in 2011) Egypt: 1998-2001 (OCDE Report Egypt 2002) Lebanon: 1995-1997 (IMF1999)

Source: Prepared by the author

The first two variables to be explained concern:

- The **SBS** defined as the ratio of GDP of the external balance of goods and services which is equal to exports of goods and services minus imports of goods and services (WDI 2021);
- The **SC** is measured by the GDP ratio of the current account balance which is the sum of net exports of goods and services, net primary income and net secondary income.

The explanatory variables are defined in the following:

- The first variable (**Cpub**) represents the ratio of general government consumption to GDP which is defined as General government final consumption expenditure (formerly general government consumption). It includes all current expenditure by general government on goods and services (including compensation of employees). It also includes most expenditure on defense and national security, but excludes general government military expenditure as part of general government capital formation;
- The second variable (**Ipub**) refers to the ratio of government investment expenditure to GDP in relation to net investment in non-financial assets of general government. It includes fixed assets, inventories, valuables and non-produced assets. Non-financial assets are stores of value and provide benefits either through their use in the production

of goods and services or in the form of property income and holding gains. Net investment in non-financial assets also includes consumption of fixed capital;

- The third explanatory variable (**PPPC**) is the price level ratio, which is the relationship between a purchasing power parity (PPP) conversion factor and a market exchange rate. It provides a measure of the differences in price levels between countries by indicating the number of units of the common currency required to purchase the same volume of the aggregate level in each country. At the GDP level, it provides a measure of the differences in the overall price levels of countries.

4. Model estimation and interpretation of results

As we discussed in paragraph (3.1) reserved for the delimitation of the models to be estimated within the framework of this research, we will first try to estimate the impact of the adjustment by public absorption of the balance of payments. At this level we will adopt the first scenario which aims at measuring the balance of the balance by the balance of goods and services, before estimating the same impact for the balance of the current account, measured by the balance of payments.

Given that we have opted for the use of advanced panel data techniques of the ECM type, the estimation of the models selected can only be carried out after an analysis of the statistical properties of the variables of the models, i.e. the stationarity test on all the series selected for each model, in accordance with the steps mentioned above at the level of the methodology.

4.1. Stationarity tests: use of panel data tests

In order to be able to carry out estimates and choose the appropriate model, it is necessary to test the stationarity of the series in order to determine the order of integration and consequently to carry out valid estimates.

The stationarity tests in a panel model are based on the unit root tests which have been developed by several authors as pointed out by Hurlin, C., & Mignon, V. (2005), mainly Levin & Lin (2002), Im-Pesaran-Shin (1997), Harris & Tzavalis (1999) and Hadri (1999).

In this context, to evaluate the order of integration of the variables selected, the tests recommended are those of Levin Lin and Chow (LLC), Peasaran (IPS) and Fisher. The results are as follows:

Table 4: Results of the stationarity tests of the variables of the two models

Variables	Statistic LLC	Prob LLC	Statistic IPS	Prob IPS	Fischer	Prob Fischer	Stationarity decision
Level variables							
SBS	0.7311	0.7676	0.7874	0.7845	22.2312	0.4462	Non
SC	-0.4677	0.3200	0.2504	0.5988	27.5670	0.1905	Non
Cpub	-0.4655	0.3208	-0.1705	-2.9634	39.9648	0.0109	Oui
Ipub	-3.5653	-3.5653	0.4323	0.0015	25.2269	0.2863	Non
PPPC	-1.1829	0.1184	0.9493	0.8288	31.6361	0.0838	Non
Variables in difference							
D(SBS)	-5.5168	0.0000	-6.9125	0.0000	84.2308	0.0000	Oui
D(SC)	-7.7443	0.0000	-6.7987	0.0000	115.8607	0.0000	Oui
d(Cpub)	-6.4967	0.0000	-8.2969	0.0000	112.7228	0.0000	Oui
d(Ipub)	-5.0978	0.0000	-7.6595	0.0000	129.7450	0.0000	Oui
D(PPPC)	-5.0662	0.0000	-5.6475	0.0000	71.5690	0.0000	Oui

Source: Compiled by the author on the basis of results from Stata.

Based on the results of the unit root tests, the following is concluded:

- The variables of SBS, SC, Ipub and PPPC are stationary after the first difference according to the three stationarity tests. Indeed, all statistics are significant at the 1% level. Otherwise, the variables are integrated of order 1;
- Concerning public consumption (Cpub), it is stationary at level I (0).

From the above, we can deduce that the results of the stationarity test inform on the opportunity to adopt an ARDL type error correction model given that the variables retained for the two models represented respectively in the two equations (3.1) and (3.2) have different integration orders.

4.2 Estimation of the equation for the adjustment of the balance of goods and services of the balance of payments by the components of public absorption

Recalling that the first model to be estimated takes as dependent variable the balance of payments measured by the ratio of GDP to the external balance of goods and services (SBS). By designating as independent variables, the two main components of public absorption by Cpub and Ipub, respectively the ratio of GDP of general public consumption of the State and the ratio of GDP of public investment expenditure, and the ratio of the price level is the ratio between a conversion factor of the purchasing power parity (PPP) and a market exchange rate (PPPC) The estimation of the adjustment relationship of the balance of goods and services of the balance of payments by the components of public absorption, for the 11 countries of the sample including Morocco, can be carried out through the equation predefined at the level of the following first model:

$$SBS_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \cdot Cpub_{it} + \beta_2 \cdot Ipub_{it} + \beta_3 \cdot PPPC_{it} + \varepsilon_{it}$$

But before estimating the equation, it is necessary to test the presence of a long-term equilibrium relationship according to the co-integration test.

4.2.1. Estimation of the long-term co-integration relationship in a panel context

The use of co-integration techniques in panel data, as highlighted by Hurlin, C., & Mignon, V. (2007), makes it possible to test for the presence of a long-term relationship between integrated variables. One of the advantages of co-integration tests on panel data is the increased power of the test. The most recognized main co-integration tests are developed by Pedroni (1999), Kao (1999) and Westerlund (2007).

The results of the co-integration relationship of the first model variables, based on these three tests, are summarised in the following table:

Table 5: Results of the co-integration tests of the 1st model variables

Kao			Pedroni			Westerlund		
Methodes	T-statistic	Prob	Méthodes	T-statistic	Prob	Méthodes	T-statistic	Prob
Modified Dickey-Fuller t	-1.6425	0.0502	Modified Phillips-Perron t	2.2533	0.0121	Variance ratio	0.7149	0.2373
Dickey-Fuller t	-1.7183	0.0429	Phillips-Perron t	0.0516	0.4794			
Augmented Dickey-Fuller t	-2.2642	0.0118	Augmented Dickey-Fuller t	0.1647	0.4346			
Unadjusted modified Dickey-Fuller t	-1.8548	0.0318						
Unadjusted Dickey-Fuller t	-1.8201	0.0344						

Source: Compiled by the author on the basis of results from Stata

The above table shows that the variables of the model are co-integrated according to the Kao test, which confirms the presence of a co-integration relationship between the balance of goods and services on the one hand, and the two main components of public absorption and the price level ratio is the ratio between a purchasing power parity (PPP) conversion factor and a market exchange rate on the other.

The presence of such a co-integration relationship will allow us to estimate the short-and long-term relationship according to three models, Pooled Mean Group (PMG), Mean Group (MG) and Dynamic Fixed Effects (DFE). The Hausman joint test will decide on the optimal model.

4.2.2. Estimation of the equation for the adjustment of the balance of goods and services

In the light of the results of the stationarity test recorded in table n°3, above, and following the results obtained, we will estimate an ARDL (1, 1, 1, 0) model. The Hausman joint test indicates that the optimal model is the dynamic fixed effect model (DFE, where prob > 5%), in accordance with the results shown in the table below:

Table 6: Result of estimation of the 1st model and the Hausman joint test

Estimation method	PMG	MG	DFE
Ajustement Coeff (ECT)	-.158146****	-.3450065****	-.2195251****
Relationship coeff Long Term			
Cpub	1.388609****	.4926454	-1.405226**
Ipub	-.2069756	3.927361**	1.761187*
PPPC	-35.25872****	20.8056	16.24829
Relationship coeff Short-Term			
dCpub(-1)	.1366501	.216246	.2143118
dIpub(-1)	-.7164328	-1.121279*	-.6512275****
d1(PPPC)	10.81955	-4.996713	-16.11551****
Constante	-2.356044*	-6.445838	.6946343
Hausman test (Prob>chi2)			
MG vs PMG	0.0085		
PMG vs DFE	0.0015		

N.B.: *, **, **** indicate significance at the 10%, 5%, 1% threshold respectively.

Source: Compiled by the author on the basis of results from Stata estimates

The results of the estimation of equation (3.1) of the adjustment of the balance of goods and services following changes in the level of public consumption and investment expenditure show that there is a relationship, both short and long term.

The results of the estimated equation are as follows:

Short-term adjustment coefficient

$$d(SBS_{it}(-1)) = .6946343 - .2195251 ECT + .2143118 d(Cpub_{it}(-1)) - .6512275 d(Ipub_{it}(-1)) - 16.11551 d(PPPC_{it})$$

Long-term adjustment coefficient

$$d(SBS_{it}(-1)) = -1.405226 Cpub_{it} + 1.761187 Ipub_{it} + 16.24829 PPPC_{it}$$

From the results reported in Table 6, above, the main conclusions are as follows:

- The long-term dynamics are significantly different from zero. The speed of adjustment between the variables for the panel of countries in the sample is significant;
- The DFE model estimators show that the GDP ratio of public investment expenditure (Ipub) lagged by one period, and the price level ratio (PPPC) impact the goods and services balance in the long run. Otherwise, every one-point increase in Ipub and PPPC respectively leads to a consequent improvement in the SBS of the order of 1.76 units and 16.24 units;
- With regard to the short-term effect, it appears that public consumption and public investment influence the balance of goods and services of the balance of payments. This

results in an improvement of 0.21 units and a deterioration of 0.65 units in the SBS following a respective increase of one unit in the Cpub and the Ipub.

4.3 Estimation of the equation for the adjustment of the current account balance by the components of public absorption

At this level, the external balance measured by the GDP ratio of the current account balance of the balance of payments will be explained by the same explanatory variables of the first model. The adjustment equation (3.2) of the second model is the following:

At this level, the external balance measured by the GDP ratio of the current account balance of the balance of payments will be explained by the same explanatory variables of the first model. The adjustment equation (3.2) of the second model is the following:

$$SC_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1.Cpub_{it} + \beta_2.Ipub_{it} + \beta_3.PPPC_{it} + \varepsilon_{it}$$

Before estimating the adjustment equation of the current account balance by the components of public absorption, it is necessary to analyse the existence of a long-term relationship through the various co-integration tests.

4.3.1 Estimation of the Long-Term cointegration relationship in a panel context

Recalling that the integration of different orders of the variables from the stationarity tests (table n°4) implies the use of a staggered lag model (ARDL).

Moreover, the estimation of the long-term cointegration relation between the variables retained at the level of the second model show the presence of a co-integration relation according to the Kao test, in particular by the three methods summarised in the table below, namely Augmented Dickey-Fuller t, Augmented Dickey-Fuller t & Unadjusted Dickey-Fuller t.

Table 7: Results of the cointegration tests of the 2nd model variables

Kao			Pedroni			Westerlund		
Methodes	T-statistic	Prob	Méthodes	T-statistic	Prob	Méthodes	T-statistic	Prob
Modified Dickey-Fuller t	-0.9981	0.1591	Modified Phillips-Perron t	1.8362	0.0332	Variance ratio	-0.1661	0.4340
Dickey-Fuller t	-1.3893	0.0824	Phillips-Perron t	-0.3942	0.3467			
Augmented Dickey-Fuller t	-2.3288	0.0099	Augmented Dickey-Fuller t	-0.3441	0.3654			
Unadjusted modified Dickey-Fuller t	-3.5697	0.0002						
Unadjusted Dickey-Fuller t	-2.7079	0.0034						

Source: Compiled by the author on the basis of results from Stata

4.2.2. Estimation of the Adjustment Equation of the Current Account Balance

Following the results of the co-integration test analysed above, the study of the adjustment relationship between the ratio of the current account balance to GDP and the two main components of public absorption recommends the adoption of an ARDL (1, 2, 2, 0) type model. Although the results in the table below show the existence of a long-term equilibrium relationship between the dependent and independent variables according to the three estimation methods (PMG, MG and DFE), the examination of these results concludes that the estimators of the PMG method are more robust than those of the other methods, in accordance with the results of the Hausman joint test (prob > chi2 is greater than 5%). These results are summarised in the table below:

Table 8: Estimation result of the 2nd Model and the Hausman joint test

Estimation method	PMG	MG	DFE
Ajustement Coeff (ECT)	-.2281312***	-.4741879***	-.3239966***
Relationship coeff Long Term			
Cpub	-1.100331***	1.345313	-.1509647
Ipub	2.188578***	-2.485331	-.8481972
PPPC	-17.66484***	-26.88628	-10.51438
Relationship coeff Short-Term			
dCpub(-2)	.4223035*	.3583044**	.2400443
dIpub(-1)	-.9303434 **	.3846423	-.5786919
dIpub(-2)	.1680539	-.2933644	.2092692
d(PPPC)	-22.77294	.2916162	-19.71534***
Constante	3.224261**	2.914423	1.364622
Hausman test (Prob>chi2)			
MG vs PMG	0.2971		
PMG vs DFE	0.2922		

N.B.: *, **, *** indicate significance at the 10%, 5%, 1% threshold respectively.

Source: Compiled by the author on the basis of results estimates from Stata

Thus, using the results of the above estimates, the short- and long-term adjustment equation for the GDP ratio of the current account balance of the balance of payments is written as follows:

Short-term adjustment coefficient

$$d(SC_{it}(-1)) = .3224261 - .2281312 ECT + .4223035 d(Cpub_{it}(-2)) \\ - .9303434 d(Ipub_{it}(-1)) + .1680539 d(Ipub_{it}(-2)) \\ - 22.77294 d(PPPC_{it})$$

Long-term adjustment coefficient

$$d(SC_{it}(-1)) = -1.100331 Cpub_{it} + 2.188578 Ipub_{it} - 17.66484 PPPC_{it}$$

The reading of the results brings out the following conclusions:

- The convergence coefficient (speed of adjustment) is significantly negative, this being said that an equilibrium relationship in the long run is present between the dependent and independent variables of the adjustment equation;
- The assertion of the significant impact of the explanatory variables on the long-term interest variable, where public consumption and the PPPC ratio negatively affect the current account balance. On the other hand, the latter is positively affected by public investment;
- In terms of the short-term relationship, it is important to note that lagged public consumption and public investment have a significant effect on the current balance of payments. Indeed, any increase of one unit in the lagged C_{pub} and I_{pub} leads to an improvement of 0.42 units and a deterioration of 0.93 units in the current account of the balance of payments respectively.

5. Discussion of Results and Conclusions

In line with the main theoretical lessons of the balance of payments adjustment approach, the empirical results drawn from the estimation of the two models show that the magnitude of the two fundamental components of public absorption associated with the ratio of the PPP conversion factor price level (GDP) to the market exchange rate has a significant effect on the adjustment and evolution of the external balances of the balance of payments for the sample studied. This observation is valid regardless of the method used to measure them, either by the external balance of the balance of goods and services or by the balance of the current account of the balance of payments.

Indeed, these empirical results corroborate the prediction of the Keynesian absorption hypothesis which predicts the existence of a relationship between budget deficits and external balance of payments deficits and reject the Ricardian hypothesis that there is no link between the two deficits.

Since the choice of balance of payments adjustment policies depends on the nature of the imbalance to be resolved, policy makers are called upon to follow effective and sustained public policies where the impact assessment is simulated well in advance of the policy launch, especially on the fiscal side, and which will be consistent with the macroeconomic balance objectives. The empirical estimation results presented above focused on the origin of the external imbalance and the measures adopted by the government to address them, especially

since the MENA countries in the sample were experiencing persistent internal and external imbalances.

From the above, important economic implications can be deduced. If economic policy makers want to work towards an improvement in the external balance, a budget adjustment, whether on the revenue side and/or on the expenditure side, needs to be well studied in terms of its macroeconomic effects, especially on external balances.

In this respect, the public authorities are led to pursue the appropriate budgetary adjustment to avoid any possible slippage of the budget deficit through budgetary slippage and to identify, in due course, the measures and instruments likely to mitigate its level. These measures must be based on controlling consumption expenditure and optimising investment expenditure and on improving tax revenue.

Given that the room for manoeuvre on public revenues is limited in most MENA countries due to relatively high tax rates, action on public absorption is found at the forefront of adjustment. It is important to note, however, that action on the imported parity of this absorption can also deteriorate the fiscal balance through the decline in related government revenues, especially when a substantial share of government revenues comes from taxes on international transactions. Nevertheless, public authorities need to manage both components of this absorption.

In this context, a fiscal adjustment cannot be reduced to a simple accounting exercise where deficits are arbitrarily reduced and expenditures are adjusted to revenues, as this is an inappropriate strategy. Rather, particular attention must be paid to wasteful spending in order to ensure a proper fiscal adjustment.

However, it is important to note that the fiscal adjustment itself requires an adjustment of the external balance. This would be possible through the diversification of external revenues as well as a good strategy of reducing the components of public absorption that constitute a significant part of the goods and services imported from abroad.

Referring to the above results, it is important to identify a major paradox of adjustment through absorption of balance of payments imbalances in the sample countries. While external balances are affected in the long run by both public consumption and public investment, it is rather the latter that's mainly responsible for balance of payments imbalances in the short run. An adjustment action on this type of expenditure is likely to be detrimental to national economies since it is public investment expenditure that is able to positively affect economic growth in the

long term, particularly through its spill-over effects on the economic activity of countries, especially for MENA countries that existed in a situation of under-employment.

On the other hand, a well-prepared and well-guided technical-fiscal adjustment strategy is needed to adjust internal and external imbalances, especially in the context of MENA countries, but the sustainability of such a strategy could only be guaranteed with the combination of other socio-political and economic adjustment instruments in which good institutional governance and structural redesign of national economies take the lead and are inspired by the good practices of countries that have successfully adjusted their balance of payments balances.

References:

- (1). Abell, J. D. (1990). Twin deficits during the 1980s: An empirical investigation. *Journal of macroeconomics*, 12(1), 81-96. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0164-0704\(90\)90057-H](https://doi.org/10.1016/0164-0704(90)90057-H)
- (2). Afonso, A., Huart, F., Jalles, J. T., & Stanek, P. (2022). Twin Deficits Revisited: a role for fiscal institutions? *Journal of International Money and Finance*, 121, 102506. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jimonfin.2021.102506>
- (3). AL khatib Alkswani, M. A. (2000). The Twin Deficits Phenomenon in Petroleum Economy: Evidence from Saudi Arabia. In *Seventh Annual Conference of the Economic Research Forum: Trends and Prospects for Growth, Amman*. <https://faculty.ksu.edu.sa/>
- (4). Alexander, S. S. (1952). Effects of a Devaluation on a Trade Balance. *Staff Papers (International Monetary Fund)*, 2(2), 263–278. <https://doi.org/10.2307/3866218>
- (5). Anderson P.S (1990). *Developments in external and internal balances - a selective and eclectic review*. Bis Economic Papers No 29, Bank of International Settlements.
- (6). Bachman, D. D. (1992). Why Is the U. S. Current Account Deficit So Large? Evidence from Vector Autoregressions. *Southern Economic Journal*, 59 (2), 232–240. <https://doi.org/10.2307/1060527>.
- (7). Bahmani-Oskooee, M. (1992). What Are the Long-Run Determinants of the U.S. Trade Balance? *Journal of Post Keynesian Economics*, 15(1), 85–97. <http://www.jstor.org/stable/4538326>.
- (8). Bahmani-Oskooee, M. (1995). The Long-Run Determinants of the U.S. Trade Balance Revisited. *Journal of Post Keynesian Economics*, 17(3), 457–465. <http://www.jstor.org/stable/4538455>.
- (9). Beetsma, R. & al. (2008). The effects of public spending shocks on trade balances and budget deficits in the European Union. *Journal of the European Economic Association*, 6 (2-3), 414-423. <https://doi.org/10.1162/JEEA.2008.6.2-3.414>.
- (10). Beetsma, R., Debrun, X., Fang, X., Kim, Y., Lledó, V., Mbaye, S., & Zhang, X. (2019). Independent fiscal councils: Recent trends and performance. *European Journal of Political Economy*, 57, 53-69. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejpoleco.2018.07.004>
- (11). Blanchard, O. J. (1985). Debt, Deficits, and Finite Horizons. *Journal of Political Economy*, 93(2), 223–247. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/1832175>.
- (12). Bourguinat, H. (2007). *Finance internationale*. Paris. Edition Dalloz.

- (13). Bousnina, R., Redzepagic, S., & Gabsi, F. B. (2021). Sustainability of current account balances in MENA countries: threshold cointegration approach. *Economic Change and Restructuring*, 54(1), 241-264. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10644-020-09278-5>.
- (14). Branson, W., & al (1979). Exchange rates in the short run: Some further results. *European Economic Review*, 12(4), 395-402. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0014-2921\(79\)90029-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/0014-2921(79)90029-1).
- (15). Chinn, M.D., & Prasad, E.S. (2003). Medium-term determinants of current accounts in industrial and developing countries: an empirical exploration. *Journal of International Economics*, 59 (1), 47-76. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0022-1996\(02\)00089-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0022-1996(02)00089-2).
- (16). Daly, V., & Siddiki, J. U. (2009). The twin deficits in OECD countries: cointegration analysis with regime shifts. *Applied Economics Letters*, 16(11), 1155-1164. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13504850701349179>.
- (17). Darrat, A. F. (1988). Have Large Budget Deficits Caused Rising Trade Deficits? *Southern Economic Journal*, 54(4), 879–887. <https://doi.org/10.2307/1059523>.
- (18). Dewald, W. G., & Ulan, M. (1989). The twin-deficit illusion. *Cato J.*, 9, 689.
- (19). Dornbusch, R. (1976). Exchange rate expectations and monetary policy. *Journal of International Economics*, 6(3), 231-244. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0022-1996\(76\)90001-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/0022-1996(76)90001-5)
- (20). Dornbusch, R. (1979). Monetary policy under exchange rate flexibility. In *Managed Exchange-Rate Flexibility: The Recent Experience*, Federal Reserve. Working paper 0311 Bank of Boston, pp. 90-122, 1978. DOI 10.3386/w0311.
- (21). Duguet, E. (2014). *Econométrie appliquée des données de panel*. <http://emmanuel.duguet.free.fr/EcPanels.pdf>
- (22). Enders, W., & Lee, B.-S. (1990). Current Account and Budget Deficits: Twins or Distant Cousins? *The Review of Economics and Statistics*, 72(3), 373–381. <https://doi.org/10.2307/2109344>.
- (23). Eyraud, L., Debrun, M. X., Hodge, A., Lledo, V. D., & Pattillo, M. C. A. (2018). *Second-generation fiscal rules: Balancing simplicity, flexibility, and enforceability*. International Monetary Fund. <https://doi.org/10.5089/9781484350683.006>.
- (24). Forte, F., & Magazzino, C. (2013). Twin Deficits in the European Countries. *International Advances in Economic Research*, 19 (3), 289-310. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11294-013-9406-3>.

- (25). Frenkel, J. & Johnson, H. (1976), *The Monetary Approach to the balance of payments*, London, George Allen & Unwin Ltd. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9780203464182>.
- (26). Hadri, K. (1999). *Testing The Null Hypothesis Of Stationarity Against The Alternative Of A Unit Root In Panel Data With Serially Correlated Errors* (No. 1999_05). University of Liverpool, Department of Economics.
- (27). Harris, R. D., & Tzavalis, E. (1999). Inference for unit roots in dynamic panels where the time dimension is fixed. *Journal of Econometric*, 91(2), 201-226. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0304-4076\(98\)00076-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0304-4076(98)00076-1)
- (28). Hurlin, C., & Mignon, V. (2005). Une synthèse des tests de racine unitaire sur données de panel. *Economie prévisions*, (3), 253-294. <https://doi.org/10.3917/ecop.169.0253>.
- (29). Hurlin, C., & Mignon, V. (2007). Une synthèse des tests de cointégration sur données de panel. *Economie prévisions*, (4), 241-265. <https://doi.org/10.3917/ecop.180.0241>.
- (30). Johnson, H.G. (1958). Toward a General Theory of the Balance of Payments. in *International Trade and Economic Growth: Studies in Pure Theory*. Allen & Unwin. London.
- (31). Kao, C., & McCoskey, S. (1999). A Monte Carlo comparison of tests for cointegration in panel data. Available at SSRN 1807953. McCoskey, Suzanne and Kao, Chihwa D., A Monte Carlo Comparison of Tests for Cointegration in Panel Data (March 1, 1999). <https://ssrn.com/abstract=1807953> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.1807953>
- (32). Kaufmann, S. & al. (2002). The Austrian current account deficit: Driven by twin deficits or by intertemporal expenditure allocation? *Empirical Economics*, 27 (3), 529-542. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s001810100094>.
- (33). Keynes, J. M. (1936). The general theory of interest, employment and money.
- (34). Kim, K. H. (1995). On the long-run determinants of the US trade balance: a comment. *Journal of Post Keynesian Economics*, 17(3), 447-455. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01603477.1995.11490039>.
- (35). Kim, S., & Roubini, N. (2008). Twin deficit or twin divergence? Fiscal policy, current account, and real exchange rate in the U.S. *Journal of International Economics*, 74 (2), 362-383. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jinteco.2007.05.012>.
- (36). Kouassi, E., Mougoue, M., & Kymn, K. O. (2004). Causality tests of the relationship between the twin deficits. *Empirical Economics*, 29(3), 503-525. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00181-003-0181-5>.
- (37). Krugman, P. & Obstfeld, M. (1994). *International Economics*.

- (38). L'Heriteau, M. F. (1986). *Le Fonds Monétaire International et les pays du Tiers Monde*. Paris. Collection tiers monde. 1^{ère} Edition. PUF. P: 142.
- (39). Levin, A., Lin, C. F., & Chu, C. S. J. (2002). Unit root tests in panel data: asymptotic and finite-sample properties. *Journal of Econometric*, 108(1), 1-24. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0304-4076\(01\)00098-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0304-4076(01)00098-7)
- (40). Mansouri, B. (2003). Soutenabilité, déterminants et implications macro-économiques des déficits publics dans les pays en voie de développement : cas du Maroc, Thèse de Doctorat d'Etat, Université Hassan II Ain Chock, FSJES, Casablanca.
- (41). Mill, J. S. (1849). *Principles of Political Economy: With Some of Their Applications to Social Philosophy: in Two Volumes* (Vol. 1). Parker.
- (42). Miller, S. M., & Russek, F. S. (1989). Are the twin deficits really related? *Contemporary Economic Policy*, 7(4), 91-115.
- (43). Muller, G. J. (2008). Understanding the dynamic effects of government spending on foreign trade. *Journal of international money and finance*, 27(3), 345-371. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jimonfin.2008.01.005>.
- (44). Mussa, M. (1974). A monetary approach to balance-of-payments analysis. *Journal of Money, Credit and Banking*, 6(3), 333-351. <https://doi.org/10.2307/1991173>
- (45). Nickel, C., & Tudyka, A. (2014). Fiscal stimulus in times of high debt: Reconsidering multipliers and twin deficits. *Journal of Money, Credit and Banking*, 46(7), 1313-1344. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jmcb.12148>
- (46). Nickel, C., & Vansteenkiste, I. (2008). Fiscal policies, the current account and Ricardian equivalence. ECB Working Paper no. 935. <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.1243262>
- (47). Normandin, M. (1999). Budget deficit persistence and the twin deficits hypothesis. *Journal of International Economics*, 49(1), 171-193. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0022-1996\(98\)00058-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0022-1996(98)00058-0)
- (48). Nyahoho, E. (2002). *Finance Internationale : théorie, politique et pratique*. Québec. Presse Universitaire du Québec.
- (49). Pedroni, P. (1999). Critical values for cointegration tests in heterogeneous panels with multiple regressors. *Oxford Bulletin of Economics and statistics*, 61(S1), 653-670. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1468-0084.0610s1653>
- (50). Pesaran, M. H., Shin, Y., & Smith, R. P. (1997). Pooled mean group estimation of dynamic heterogeneous panels. *Journal of the American statistical Association*, 94(446), 621-634. DOI: 10.1080/01621459.1999.10474156.

- (51). Pirotte, A. (1999). Convergence of the static estimation toward the long run effects of dynamic panel data models. *Economics letters*, 63(2), 151-158. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0165-1765\(99\)00023-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0165-1765(99)00023-3)
- (52). Polak, J. J. (1957). Monetary Analysis of Income Formation and Payments Problems. *Staff Papers (International Monetary Fund)*, 6(1), 1–50. <https://doi.org/10.2307/3866128>
- (53). Ricardo, D. (1821). *On the principles of political economy*. London: J. Murray.
- (54). Robinson, J. (1937). The foreign exchanges. In *Essays in the Theory of Employment* London: Macmillan. Reprinted in *Readings in the Theory of International Trade* (H. S. Ellis and L. A. Metzler, eds.), pp. 83-103. Philadelphia: Blakiston,
- (55). Rosensweig, J. A., & Tallman, E. W. (1993). Fiscal policy and trade adjustment: are the deficits really twins? *Economic Inquiry* 31(4), Western Economic Association International, 580-594. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1465-7295.1993.tb00892.x>
- (56). Roubini, N. (1991). Economic and political determinants of budget deficits in developing countries. *Journal of International money and Finance*, 10, S49-S72. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0261-5606\(91\)90046-M](https://doi.org/10.1016/0261-5606(91)90046-M).
- (57). Smith, A. (1937). *The wealth of nations [1776]* (Vol. 11937).
- (58). Vamvoukas, G. A. (1999). The twin deficits phenomenon: evidence from Greece. *Applied economics*, 31(9), 1093-1100. <https://doi.org/10.1080/000368499323571>.
- (59). Westerlund, J., & Edgerton, D. L. (2007). A panel bootstrap cointegration test. *Economics letters*, 97(3), 185-190. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.econlet.2007.03.003>
- (60). Zietz, J., & Pemberton, D. K. (1990). The U. S. Budget and Trade Deficits: A Simultaneous Equation Model. *Southern Economic Journal*, 57(1), 23–34. <https://doi.org/10.2307/1060475>